

AN ESSAY ON THE ROLE OF FOLKLORE IN SOFTWARE ENGINEERING: PRECONCEPTIONS AND THEIR MEANING IN SOFTWARE TESTING AND TEST AUTOMATION

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ABSTRACT. The craft of engineering software has accumulated a rich folklore (i.e., shared narratives, humor, rituals, myths, superstitions, and informal heuristics) that circulate among programmers, testers, and managers. These cultural artifacts seem to influence how teams interpret metrics, make architectural decisions, and adopt tools and methodologies. Drawing on ethnographic research, folklore studies, and industry collaboration, this essay explores various categories of software folklore, including narratives, myths, humor, rituals, and superstitions. By surfacing and examining these informal elements, the essay aims to distinguish both heuristics and outdated myths in software engineering as well as software testing and test automation, enabling teams to evolve their practices with both cultural self-awareness and practical grounding.

Keywords. Folklore, Software Engineering Practices, Rituals, Knowledge

1. INTRODUCTION

Like other professions, software engineering has developed its own set of shared stories, beliefs, jokes, and myths [1, 2, 3]. These cultural artifacts, from anecdotes to persistent myths, circulate among developers, testers, and managers. Though some of them are often dismissed as unscientific, they still seem to shape professional identity, decision-making, and how practitioners understand their work.

Early definitions of folklore focused on the antiquity, anonymity, and simplicity of folklore, often associating it with "popular antiquities" [4]. There seem to be three basic ways to conceptualize folklore: (1) a body of knowledge held in common or shared wisdom, (2) a mode of thought expressed through collective representations, and (3) an almost art form that is part of a creative process. The criteria for defining folklore relate to its social context, particularly the structure of the groups in which it arises, geographical, ethnic, and occupational. Folklore seems to thrive in small groups where direct, face-to-face communication is possible [5]. Oral tradition and initiation, in some cases, are critical, distinguishing folklore from written literature and classic media. Folklore should not be seen as a collection of static objects but as a dynamic communication process that involves interaction between humans in a shared cultural context. In some software engineering communities, communication is evident in how practitioners

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exchange knowledge, tell stories, create rituals, and develop shared language to navigate complex socio-technical environments. This perspective that emanates from Ben Amos' work [4] highlights that folklore is actively created, recreated, and performed in workplaces, providing insights into how engineers navigate both the technical and human complexities of their profession.

In this essay, I argue that understanding software engineering folklore is essential, particularly in the current context where artificial intelligence tools are reshaping software development and testing practices. By recognizing the narratives behind the use of metrics and tools in software engineering, particularly in software testing and test automation, we can distinguish between helpful heuristics and outdated or misleading assumptions.

2. FOLKLORE AND METRICS

Software engineering relies heavily on metrics to measure progress, quality, and risk [6]. However, once metrics are mythologized, they can become counterproductive. A persistent belief is that some developers are 10x more productive than others [2]. Additionally, some teams may regard high test coverage as an indicator of quality, overlooking the broader context and potential limitations of what test coverage measures¹. Humor is often the bond that unites many professional communities, and software professionals are no exception. Developers and testers have developed a rich body of jokes², puns, and sayings that entertain and impart folk wisdom³. Beyond stories and jokes, software developers have developed customary practices, some formal and some informal, that carry almost ritualistic significance⁴. The folklore about metrics involves the informal transmission of such knowledge, usually outside of formal educational settings. Multiple existences and variations characterize folklore. For example, the folklore items mentioned previously in this section gain legitimacy through their transmission across groups and generations, with each iteration potentially changing to suit new contexts. Researching folklore can reveal underlying values, norms, and psychological patterns; for example, showing how traditions reflect collective fears and desires and uncovering cultural assumptions and social structures that official accounts and formal documents may obscure.

¹A common myth is that high test coverage implies high-quality test cases. However, researchers (e.g., [7]) and practitioners (e.g., <https://martinfowler.com/bliki/TestCoverage.html>) have repeatedly challenged this.

²It Works on My Machine! became a concept capturing environment and configuration issues. You can often find this on T-shirts or memes, and it spreads informally. It highlights the gap between local setups and real deployment conditions.

³A Tester Walks into a Bar... is an example of a joke in software testing: the tester orders zero beers, 99999 beers, and negative beers, yet misses the real scenario when a customer asks for the bathroom. The bar catches fire and everyone dies. It highlights the importance of real-world end-to-end scenarios. Variations of this joke are shared widely in software engineering and testing communities and forums (e.g., Ministry of Testing).

⁴An example of a ritual is the daily stand-up; although it is described in the official scrum guide [8], it has taken on a ritualistic status in many teams in software development.

3. TOWARDS DEFINING FOLKLORE IN SOFTWARE ENGINEERING

Software engineering has long depended on metrics to assess progress, quality, and risks, and while these measures can provide valuable insights, we see that they often evolve beyond their original intent. Over time, what begins as a reasonable rule of thumb may become an unquestioned best practice or even a myth. When metrics and practices become mythologized, they risk turning into cargo cult rituals applied uncritically, without regard for context or evidence. This dynamic process emphasizes a more general phenomenon: the circulation of beliefs, stories, and practices within software engineering communities that shape behavior, regardless of their grounding. In other words, what I am trying to underscore in this essay is the need to understand software engineering folklore.

Software engineering folklore *refers to traditional knowledge embedded in and expressed through the repeated, socially and materially situated practices of software professionals.* It highlights knowledge in practice, specifically cognitive and cultural understandings that are transmitted informally through multimodal ⁵ forms [9]. These practices are not just habitual but actions whose repetition across contexts signals shared values, tacit expertise, and professional identity within the software development community.

In response to Bronner [9], I offer a practice-oriented formula: folklore in software engineering is the informally transmitted knowledge and practices shared among occupational groups within software development environments. This includes both the informal transmission of cultural expressions and the active embodiment of knowledge through repeated adaptive and symbolic practices. Here, shared traditions could shape group identity, guide team behavior, and support practitioners in navigating complex technical and organizational contexts. Proposing such a definition is essential in studying knowledge as a core resource of software engineering. It allows for both verbal material, digital, and written forms of folklore and makes room for both collective and individual types of knowledge. One problem with defining folklore in this way is that we do not include too much in terms of behaviors. We need to distinguish it from popular culture, while at the same time making its analysis more social and ethnographic.

4. PRECONCEPTIONS AND BELIEFS AS SOFTWARE TESTING FOLKLORE

As an instantiation of software engineering folklore, testing folklore contains the traditional knowledge that emerges from, and is supported through, the repeated practices of software testers. In this way, we draw attention to knowledge in practice as well as cognitive and cultural understandings that are shared and transmitted informally across different forms of interaction and expression between software testers. We selected several preconceptions in Table 1. The preconceptions about software testing highlighted in the interview study by Swillus

⁵Multimodal refers to oral, written, visual, and demonstrative forms of communication.

TABLE 1. Examples of Preconception-related Folklore Items related to Software Testing and Test Automation.

Folklore Item	Description
Testing as <i>Lesser Task</i>	Perception that testing is of lesser intellectual significance, often assigned to less experienced developers.
Extensive Testing as <i>Poor Development</i>	Belief that extensive testing indicates inadequate initial development or design practices.
<i>Mistrust</i> of Test Automated Tools	Skepticism towards automated testing tools based on informally circulated negative experiences or anecdotes.
Testing <i>Does Not Add Value</i>	Belief that testing is not valuable in the software development lifecycle.
Testing <i>Equals Checking</i>	Misconception that testing is only about verifying predefined conditions.
Testing is <i>for Non-coders</i>	The belief that testing is for programmers who cannot code.
<i>Sole Responsibility</i> of Testers	View that testing is only the responsibility of testers, not a collaborative effort.
Testing Is <i>Boring and Easy</i>	Perception that testing lacks complexity and critical thinking.
Testing <i>Increases Quality</i>	Oversimplification that testing alone increases quality without recognizing its multifaceted contributions.
Manual Testing Has <i>No Value</i>	Bias towards automation, undervaluing the insights from manual testing.

et al. [10] exemplify some folklore within software testing. One such preconception belief is the perception that testing is primarily an activity of lesser intellectual significance, often relegated to junior or less experienced developers. This notion, communicated informally through stories, jokes, and attitudes among software developers, captures a deeply embedded cultural bias. Such beliefs, when repeatedly articulated through casual conversations circulating within software communities, reinforce the folklore that testing is secondary to design and development tasks. Also, Swillus et al. highlight the assumption that extensive testing indicates poor initial development or inadequate design practices. This preconception could persist through shared narratives about the *ideal* development process, where quality is presumed inherent rather than demonstrably validated through rigorous testing procedures.

Folkloric transmission of these beliefs occurs informally, not only through explicit statements during meetings but also through implicit means such as management decisions, recognition patterns, and casual interactions within development teams. Such preconceptions reinforce a culture where testing is perceived as an undesirable necessity rather than an integral part of software quality assurance. Another folklore item involves the mistrust of automated testing tools. Informally circulated anecdotes about tool failures, limitations, or false positives significantly shape skepticism. These stories, frequently recounted in informal

settings, carry experiential weight. Consequently, these could contribute to skepticism towards test automation solutions, impacting their adoption and integration into established software practices.

Beyond these, additional preconceptions identified by Enoiu et al. [11] exemplify folklore within software testing. One such preconception is the belief that testing does not add value, undermining its importance within the software development lifecycle. Another misconception equates testing merely with checking, implying that it involves only verifying predefined conditions rather than a broader exploration to uncover potential issues. Additionally, a prevalent folklore is that testing is for non-coders, suggesting it is primarily suited for programmers who lack strong coding skills. This notion further isolates testing from the broader software development community. A notable folklore item is the view that testing is the sole responsibility of testers, thereby ignoring the collaborative effort essential for effective quality assurance. Another widespread perception is that testing is inherently boring and easy, underestimating the complexity and critical thinking required for thorough testing practices. Additionally, the oversimplification that testing alone increases software quality ignores the multifaceted contributions and interactions needed for comprehensive software quality assurance. Lastly, a bias towards automation frequently results in the undervaluation of manual testing, disregarding the crucial insights manual practices provide. The informal transmission of these preconceptions through discussions or repetitive practices in software testing could continually spread these beliefs. This folklore not only seems to shape cognitive and cultural attitudes but also could influence professional identity, values, and everyday software testing practices. Recognizing these preconceptions as folklore could provide an essential lens for understanding and addressing implicit cultural dynamics, fostering critical reflection, and promoting cultural and professional evolution within software testing communities.

5. IMPLICATIONS FOR RESEARCH

For researchers in empirical software engineering studying folklore, it is essential to use both literature analysis and ethnographic fieldwork, observing how engineers talk about software engineering, quality, testing, and AI-assisted tools. Folklore elements can be categorized and validated through the feedback of practitioners. Ethnographic fieldwork is particularly suited to surfacing this folklore [12, 13], while oral history methods offer a way to trace how beliefs evolve [14]. Storytelling in software engineering can be analyzed as cultural artifacts encoding identity and critique [15]. In addition, comparative studies [16, 17] can uncover how folklore varies across domains, teams, or roles.

Research on software engineering folklore should explore day-to-day practices and occupational behaviors through ethnographic observation to identify humor, storytelling, and rituals that create shared identity and resilience. Additional methods [18] to collect folklore items:

- Expert Interviews. Used these to gather deeper stories, anecdotes, and traditions directly from practitioners using semi-structured or open-ended

interviews focusing on lore. In these interviews, researchers should ask about common knowledge or unwritten rules.

- Focus Groups. Use these to bring together practitioners for a guided discussion around unwritten best practices or widely circulated jokes and rituals. These group discussions can spark recollection of additional folklore items.
- Observational Studies as Ethnography. Use these to capture folklore as it is enacted in the real world. Researchers can participate or observe teams over an extended period.
- Surveys. Use these to gather broad perceptions of lore teams or confirm how widespread certain beliefs are.
- Digital ethnography. Use this to explore online communities and find repeated folklore items while observing patterns where the same piece of common knowledge appears repeatedly.

Together, these approaches point to a rich research agenda for understanding the social and cultural underpinnings of software engineering folklore.

6. CONCLUSION

As we increasingly adopt AI tools and navigate complex software development environments, the folklore that shapes our work becomes more consequential. Acknowledging the interplay between folklore, metrics, and emerging technology (i.e., LLM-based test automation) should allow us to reveal how practices shape software engineering work processes.

As Lloyd [18] highlights the professional role of folklorists, I propose in this essay that software engineering researchers and educators should also engage in field-based investigations: uncovering folklore, working in applied settings, and contributing to policy, community development, and the preservation of evidence-based heuristics. Such efforts require ethnographic fieldwork complemented by collaborative data collection, archival research, and the use of online sources, enabling both quantitative and qualitative research questions to be addressed.

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⁶Software Center (<https://www.software-center.se/>) is a collaborative partnership between academia and industry aimed at accelerating the adoption of state-of-the-art software engineering practices in participating organizations.

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